

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES AND WEAR BEHAVIOR OF ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

In this study, Al/Al₂O₃, Al/SiC, and Al/SiC/Al₂O₃ composite materials were fabricated by the squeeze infiltration method. Tensile tests at room and elevated temperatures were performed. Strength of MMCs decreases with the testing temperature. However, still it has reasonable value to use for high temperature applications. Reductions of strength are mainly on account of overaging and softening of the matrix. By the dry spindle wear test, wear behaviors were characterized under the various testing conditions (volume fractions of reinforcements, sliding distances, and sliding speeds). Wear resistance of Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC composites is improved due to the presence of reinforcements. Also, Al/SiC composites have better wear resistance than Al/Al₂O₃. The major wear mechanisms of discontinuous MMCs are strongly dependent of sliding speeds. At the low speed, adhesive and abrasive wear mechanisms are dominant, and melt and seizure wear mechanism at the high speed. While wear resistances of Al alloys decrease as the sliding speed increases, those of MMCs increased due to superior mechanical properties and good thermal stability of reinforcements. Weight loss is linearly increased with the sliding distance. Wear behaviors of hybrid composites were compared with those of Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC composites. The results of this study will be used to understand the basic wear behavior of MMCs and eventually to expand the application of MMCs as machine parts.

KEYWORDS : Metal matrix composites ; Squeeze casting ; Tensile strength ; Wear Behaviour ; Wear mechanism

1. INTRODUCTION

Aluminum alloys are very suitable for applications which require light weight and energy savings because of their low density. Their applications have been often limited due to their low mechanical properties at room and elevated temperatures. However, aluminum alloys can meet various demands of many applications by the addition of reinforcements which have

superior mechanical properties and good thermal stabilities. Al matrix composites have possessed improved mechanical properties as compared to properties of unreinforced metals. These improved properties are including; i) high specific modulus and strength, ii) retentions of properties at elevated temperatures, and iii) wear resistance [1].

In previous investigations, it was shown that the incorporation of both hard ceramic reinforcements [2-10] and soft lubricants [11-13] into an aluminum alloy improved the wear resistance. Effect of particle sizes on wear behaviour was considered [2,3]. According to them, the wear resistance increased with volume fractions and sizes of reinforcements. It was found that a major wear mechanism was the abrasion wear in Al/SiC and Al/Al₂O₃ particulate composites. Up to now, effect of reinforcements' hardness or types of reinforcements on wear behaviour have not been understood clearly. The wear resistance of Al/Al₂O₃ composites was found to be superior to that of Al/SiC composites because of brittle interface between the SiC particle and the aluminum alloy matrix [4]. But, there is another study which suggested Al/SiC particulate composites had slightly superior wear resistance due to greater hardness of SiC.

Effect of SiC whiskers on the wear resistance of Al/SiC whisker composites were found due to (1) high wear resistance of SiC whisker itself, i.e., superior hardness, and (2) uniform distributions of SiC whiskers which were found to be a barrier against the slip of SiC particles [9]. The wear resistance of Al/SiC whisker, Al/Al₂O₃ fiber, and Al/SiC/Al₂O₃ hybrid composites was considered in their later investigation [10]. From their results, SiC whiskers were more effective in improving the wear resistance than Al₂O₃ fibers. However, the wear resistance of hybrid composites is superior to that of Al/SiC composites. the effect of SiC whiskers in the hybrid composite was regarded as a barrier against the slip of Al₂O₃ fibers.

Wear mechanisms of fiber reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) are considered to be different from those of particle reinforced MMCs. For applications which require for both high mechanical properties and good wear resistance, the wear mechanism of fiber reinforced MMCs should be identified. In this study, to identify wear behaviours of fiber reinforced MMCs clearly, abrasive wear tests were carried out with various test conditions. Wear behaviour of Al/SiC, Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC/Al₂O₃ composites are discussed. Wear mechanisms of discontinuous MMCs are suggested by the examinations of worn surfaces.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials Preparation Discontinuous MMCs used in this study were prepared by the direct squeeze infiltration method. Matrix was a 6061 aluminum alloy, and SiC whiskers and alumina fibers were used as reinforcements. SiC whiskers, Tokawhisker, was from TEXTRON Specialty Materials Co. and alumina fibers, "Saffil" RF Grade, from ICI Co.. Their specifications are listed in Table 1. Microstructure of discontinuous MMCs was observed through the optical microscope to examine distribution of reinforcements. Surfaces normal to and parallel with the pressure direction were looked into with the view for identifying effects of applied pressure on the orientation of reinforcements. To examine variations of local volume fractions in a single casting, specimens were observed along the height. Specimens were polished with emery papers (from 600 to 1200) and up to 0.05 μm alumina particles.

2.2 Tensile Test Room temperature tensile tests were performed with MTS 809 Axial Torsional Test System. Test were load controlled and the load rate was 30 N / sec. Strain gages were attached in the center of the gage length section. High temperature tensile tests were carried out with INSTRON, Model No. 1127, at 150 °C and 300 °C. They were displacement controlled and the displacement rate was 0.5 mm / min. Heat treatments of specimens were the T6 heat treatment for the room temperature test, and the solution treatment, the T6 heat treatment, and overaging for the high temperature test. Specimens were machined perpendicular to the direction of applied pressure.

2.3 Abrasive Wear Test Dry abrasive wear tests were carried out with the spindle type wear tester, Universal Wear Tester from Riken - Ogoshi Co., at the room temperature. Simple schematic illustration for the spindle type wear tester is shown in Figure 1. The electronic balance which is able to weigh up to 10^5 g was used to measure weight loss of composites. Specimens with dimensions of $50 \times 20 \times 6$ (mm) were machined perpendicular and parallel to the direction of the applied pressure. Their surfaces were polished by emery paper (#600) to achieve the same surface condition. Oil quenched SCM 4 (550 Hv) and 304 stainless steel (160Hv) were used as counter materials, discs. Here, SCM 4 is equivalent to AISI 4140.

Abrasive wear tests were performed under the followings conditions ; (1) the final load ; 3.2 kgf, sliding distance ; 100 m, sliding speed ; 0.94 m/s, and various volume fractions of reinforcements ; 0.12 - 0.20. (2) the final load ; 3.2 kgf, sliding distance ; 100 m, and various sliding speeds ; 0.08-1.98 m/s. (3) the final load ; 3.2 kgf, sliding speed ; 0.94 m/s, and various sliding distances ; 100, 200, 400 m. After the abrasive wear tests, the weight loss was measured and the worn surfaces were examined to investigate the state of surfaces and suggest the dominant wear mechanism.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure Typical microstructures of Al/SiC, Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC/Al₂O₃ composites are represented in Figure 2. The uniform distribution of reinforcements and good bondings between the matrix alloy and reinforcements are achieved. The reinforcements are uniformly distributed along the height of the cast, i.e., negligible variations of local volume fractions. Insignificant variations of local volume fractions are due to the homogeneity of the preform which can be obtained by the adequate pressure and the sufficient mixing of reinforcements.

3.2 Mechanical Properties The tensile properties of T6 tempered composites are shown in Figure 3. In our previous work[14], mechanical properties such as young's modulus and tensile strength of MMCs were improved up to 70 % and 60 % in Al/SiC, and 35 % and 25 % in Al/Al₂O₃ composites by the addition of reinforcements, respectively. The SiC whisker additions were more effective in strengthening than Al₂O₃ fiber. However, the tensile strength of composites reinforced with a hybrid of SiC whiskers and Al₂O₃ fibers, as shown in Figure 3, was approximately equal to that of the Al/SiC composites reinforced with the same volume fraction.

Ceramic fibers reinforced metal matrix composites have superior high temperature properties to the unreinforced matrix alloy because ceramic reinforcements exhibit good thermal stabilities. Because Al/SiC and Al/Al₂O₃ have faster aging rate than the unreinforced Al alloy, an overaging starts to occur if aluminum matrix composites are solution treated and aged at 180 °C for more than 4 hours and at 300 °C for 30 minutes. Therefore, MMCs will be overaged during the service when age hardenable alloy matrix composites, such as aluminum and magnesium base composites, are used in the high temperature application. In this study, to simulate the real service condition, high temperature tensile tests were performed with overaged specimens.

Figure 4.(a) shows the effect of testing temperatures on ultimate tensile strength of Al/SiC and Al/Al₂O₃ composites. As shown in this figure, Al/SiC and Al/Al₂O₃ composites show better high temperature tensile strength than the unreinforced matrix alloy. And tensile strengths of discontinuous MMCs at 150 °C and 300 °C maintain their 85 % and 70 % level of tensile strength at room temperature in Al/SiC composites, and 80 % and 40 % in Al/Al₂O₃ composites, respectively. It is shown that discontinuous MMCs still have reasonable values for high temperature applications. The effect of heat treatments on high temperature strength of MMCs are shown in Figure 4. (b). At 150 °C, tensile strength of solution treated specimens is greater than that of overaged. Because solution treated specimens are on the way of age hardening during heating and testing, and this hardening compensates the reduction of strength. But at 300 °C, tensile strength of solution treated is almost the same as overaged because solution treated specimens are already overaged during raising a temperature and

testing. From this figure, the reduction of high temperature strength, A - C, can be regarded as the sum of strength reductions due to the overaging, A - B, and softening of the matrix alloy, B - C. Namely, main factors for the strength reduction at elevated temperatures are overaging and softening of the matrix alloy.

3.3 Wear Behaviours Because the wear resistance of aluminum alloys is extremely poor, their applications as structural materials and machine parts are oftenly limited. Fortunately, it is demonstrated from abrasive wear tests under diverse conditions that the wear resistance of discontinuous MMCs is improved remarkably by the incorporation of reinforcements.

Effect of the volume fraction of reinforcements on wear behaviour is represented in Figure 5. At sliding speed, 0.94 m/s, when counter material is SCM 4, wear resistances of discontinuous MMCs are improved up to 580 % and 1120 %, respectively. It is due to reinforcements which can endure the friction force generated on the wear surface. This friction force plays an important role in wear behaviour, specially in the abrasive wear. Generally, the higher the friction force is generated, the worse the wear resistance is. The effect of reinforcements incorporation on wear resistance is getting less notable at high volume fraction, which agrees with results of other [6].

As shown in Figure 6, it is interesting to note that the wear resistance of the composite reinforced with a hybrid of Al_2O_3 fibers and SiC whiskers was superior to that of the Al/SiC composite reinforced the same volume fraction. The wear resistance of hybrid composites was improved by the addition of reinforcements, as shown in Figure 7. The hybrid composites of SiC whiskers and Al_2O_3 fibers was more effective than that in the composites reinforced with a single species of reinforcements.

Figure 8 show effects of sliding distances on weight losses of 6061 Al alloy and Al/15vol.% SiC composites under the final load, 3.2 kgf, and the sliding speed, 0.94 m/s. As shown in this figure, weight losses of both materials increase linearly with the sliding distance. Effect of heat treatments is less distinguished in Al/SiC composite than in 6061 Al alloy because of superior effect of reinforcements on the improvement in the wear resistance.

Figure 9 illustrates effect of sliding speeds on wear behaviour of 6061 Al alloy, Al/SiC and Al/ Al_2O_3 composites. In this figure, wear behaviour are changed along sliding speeds. It means that wear mechanisms are strongly dependent upon the sliding speed. Major wear mechanisms of an Al alloy are adhesive and abrasive wears at sliding speeds up to 1 m/s, therefore, a 6061 Al alloy is worn by the friction force generated on the wear surface. Above the sliding speed, 1 m/s, the major wear mechanism is shifted into the melt wear because of the ascent of the temperature on the localized wear surface. Consequently, a 6061 Al alloy starts to be worn out abruptly.

In discontinuous MMCs, weight loss is greater than that of the unreinforced matrix alloy at low sliding speed, up to about 0.37 m/s, because reinforcements abrade the matrix by the high friction force and this abrasion deteriorates the wear resistance of discontinuous MMCs. At low sliding speeds, the friction force generated on the wear surface is large enough to abrade the surface of the composite. As the sliding speed increases, the friction force becomes weakened due to the reduction of the friction coefficient, and reinforcements can put up with the weak friction force. In consequence, weight loss decreases until the melt wear becomes the major mechanism for wear. At high sliding speeds (> 1.98 m/s), the wear resistance get worse, weight loss starts to increase, due to the melt wear and seizure of the matrix alloy. But the high thermal stability and superior mechanical properties of reinforcements make the deterioration of the wear resistance feeble.

Effects of sliding speeds on wear behaviour of Al/SiC, and Al/SiC/ Al_2O_3 composites are shown in Figure 10. This figure shows the same trend of the wear in Al/SiC composites as that shown in the previous figure. Therefore, the wear mechanisms are independent of counter

material types. Also, the effect of heat treatments on wear behaviour in Al/SiC composite is negligible under various sliding speeds because reinforcements play the major role in wear behaviour as shown in this figure.

When a 304 stainless steel is used as a counter material, weight loss is greater than those when a SCM 4 is used. These phenomena are in virtue of the mutual abrasion between counter materials and specimens. Generally, SiC whiskers and Al_2O_3 fibers have very high hardnesses, 2800 Hv and 1600 Hv, respectively. In consequence, a 304 stainless steel (180 Hv) is more apt to be abraded by reinforcements than SCM 4 (550Hv). It is considered that the damaged surface of counter materials and particles from abrasions of counter materials accelerates to form grooves on the wear surface.

3.4 Wear Surface Analysis Wear surfaces of both Al/SiC and Al/ Al_2O_3 composites are examined by SEM. Figure 11 represent overall wear surfaces of Al/20vol.%SiC and Al/20vol.% Al_2O_3 composites at various sliding speeds, 0.08, 0.94 and 1.98m/s. Also wear surfaces of Al/20vol.% Al_2O_3 composites at high magnification are shown in Figure 12. Generally, both composites show the almost same behaviour. At low sliding speed, 0.08 m/s, severe damages of wear surface in both composites are found. The removal of the material is progressed by the fracture of reinforcements and the matrix which might be due to the high friction force applied on the wear surface (Figure 11 (a),(d)). Surface damages in Al/ Al_2O_3 are much more severe than those in Al/SiC. It can be considered that delamination caused by the excessive fracture of reinforcements and the matrix deteriorate the wear resistance of metal matrix composites at the low sliding speed (Figure 12 (a)).

At the intermediate sliding speed, 0.94 m/s, the damaged section on the wear surface is reduced as shown in Figure 11 (b) and (e). Grooves are also observed in these figures. Grooves in Al/20 vol.% Al_2O_3 are more distinguished than Al/SiC. It is due to inferior mechanical properties of Al_2O_3 fibers to SiC whiskers. From the wear surface, it can be regarded that groove plays an important role in wear behaviour, i.e., wear is progressed by its formation and growth. The groove formation and growth are illustrated in Figure 12 (b) and (c). The groove is formed at the locally fractured area of reinforcements and the matrix. Although less friction forces apply on the wear surface, this localized fracture is taken place by high localized friction forces which come from the ununiform surface of the counter material and defected areas of the wear surface. The groove growth is advanced by the fracture of the wear surface at the end of the groove and along the groove (Figure 12 (c)). Wear surfaces represent that the adhesive - abrasive wear is the dominant wear mechanism at low and intermediate sliding speeds.

Wear surfaces at the sliding speed, 1.98 m/s, are shown in Figure 11 (c) and (f). Localized melted areas are observed owing to the high sliding speed in both composites. As shown in Figure 12 (d), the wear is started by localized melting of the surface and proceed by delaminations from seizure or the large plastic deformation of the matrix. Also, the fracture of reinforcements and matrix is seldom observed due to the remarkable reduction of friction forces applied on the wear surface. Small grooves which might be related to precipitates, indicated by an arrow, are often shown (Figure 12 (d)). These figures show that major wear mechanisms at high sliding speeds are the melt wear and the seizure of the matrix.

The outstanding wear resistance of composites reinforced with a hybrid of SiC whiskers and Al_2O_3 fibers was investigated by observation of wear surfaces in Figure 14. The wear surface of Al/ Al_2O_3 composites exhibited a number of deep wear grooves and the aluminium matrix was scratched with slipped Al_2O_3 fibers. As shown in Figure 15, this slip of Al_2O_3 fibers was observed on the surfaces of wear specimen and counter material. For a hybrid MMCs, the very fine whiskers did not cause a considerable damage to the wear surfaces between each Al_2O_3 fibers.

The outstanding wear resistance of composites reinforced with a hybrid of SiC whiskers and

Al₂O₃ fibers was investigated by observation of wear surfaces in Figure 13. The wear surface of Al/Al₂O₃ composites exhibited a number of deep wear grooves and the aluminium matrix was scratched with slipped Al₂O₃ fibers. This slip of Al₂O₃ fibers was observed on the surfaces of wear specimen and counter material. For a hybrid MMCs, the very fine whiskers did not cause a considerable damage to the wear surfaces between each Al₂O₃ fibers.

From wear surface analyses, wear behaviour of discontinuous MMCs can be summarized as follows: (i) At low speeds, wear is progressed by fractures of reinforcements and the matrix which are due to high friction forces. (ii) At intermediate speeds, the groove formation and growth are major mechanisms for wear. (iii) At high speeds, localized melting and large plastic deformations due to the high frictional heat are dominant factors for the removal of discontinuous MMCs. In other words, the major wear mechanism is the adhesive - abrasive wear up to intermediate sliding speeds and the melt wear at high speeds.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. Mechanical properties of discontinuous MMCs, such as Young's modulus, and tensile strength, are improved up to 80 % by incorporations of reinforcements.
2. Tensile strengths at 150 °C and 300 °C maintain their 85 % and 70 % level of strength at room temperature in Al/SiC composite, and 80 % and 40 % in Al/Al₂O₃ composite, respectively. Strength reduction of MMCs at elevated temperature is mainly caused by overaging and softening of the matrix alloy.
3. The wear resistance of discontinuous MMCs is remarkably improved by the addition of reinforcements. Weight loss increases linearly with the sliding distance.
4. Dominant wear mechanisms are suggested from wear surface analyses, the major wear mechanism is the adhesive-abrasive wear at low and intermediate sliding speed, and the melt wear at high sliding speeds.

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TABLE 1 Specifications of SiC whisker and Al₂O₃ fiber [15,16]

Material	Composition (wt.%)	Density (g/cm ³)	Diameter (μm)	Length (μm)
Al ₂ O ₃ (Saffil RF Grade)	Al ₂ O ₃ : 96 - 97 SiO ₂ : 3 - 4	3.3	1.5 - 6.6*	3 - 110*
			Av. 3.5	70
SiC (Tokawhisker)	SiC : 100	3.2	0.3 - 0.6*	5 - 15*
			Av. 0.45	8.4

Material	Aspect ratio (l/d)	Tensile strength (GPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Use temp. stability to (°C)
Saffil RF Grade	4 - 38*	2.0	310	1600
	Av. 20			
SiC (Tokawhisker)	10 - 25*	3 - 14	400 - 700	1600 (in air)
	Av. 13.5			

* ; Measured values from microstructures.

FIGURE 1. Schematic illustration of the abrasive wear tester

FIGURE 2. Microstructure of
(a) Al / 15 vol.% SiC,
(b) Al / 15 vol.% Al₂O₃, and
(c) Al / 5 vol.% SiC / 10 vol.% Al₂O₃
composites fabricated by the squeeze
infiltration method

FIGURE 3. Effect of the volume fraction of reinforcements on (a) Young's modulus, (b) ultimate tensile strength of MMCs

FIGURE 4. (a) Effects of testing temperature on UTS of overaged MMCs, (b) effect of heat treatments on high temperature UTS of MMCs

FIGURE 5. Effect of the volume fraction of reinforcements on wear behavior
 Final load ; 3.2 kgf,
 Sliding distance ; 100 m,
 Sliding speed ; 0.94 m/s
 Counter materials ; SCM4 and 304 stainless steel(*)

FIGURE 6. Comparison of the wear resistance of various MMCs with the same volume fraction

FIGURE 7. Effect of SiC whisker addition on wear property of hybrid composites

FIGURE 8. Effect of sliding distance on behaviour of 6061 Al and Al / SiC composites
 Final load ; 3.2 kgf,
 Sliding speed ; 0.94 m/s,
 Counter material ; 304 stainless steel

FIGURE 9. Effect of sliding speeds on wear behaviour of Al alloy and discontinuous MMCs
 Final load ; 3.2 kgf,
 Sliding distance ; 100 m,
 Counter material ; SCM4

FIGURE 10. Effect of sliding speeds on wear behaviour of discontinuous MMCs
 Final load ; 3.2 kgf,
 Sliding distance ; 100 m,
 Counter material ; 304 stainless steel

FIGURE 11. Overall wear surface of Al / 20 vol.% SiC (a,b,c) and Al / 20 vol.% Al₂O₃ (d,e,f) composites with various sliding speeds Sliding distance ; 100 m and counter material ; SCM4 (a), (d) at 0.08 m/s, (b), (e) at 0.94 m/s, and (c), (f) at 1.98 m/s

FIGURE 12. Wear surface of Al / 20 vol.% Al₂O₃ composites with various sliding speeds
Sliding distance ; 100 m and counter material ; SCM4
(a) adhesive - abrasive wear at 0.08 m/s, (b), (c) groove formation and growth at 0.94 m/s, and (d) melt wear at 1.98 m/s

FIGURE 13. Overall wear surface of Al / 5 vol.% SiC / 10 vol.% Al_2O_3 composites with various sliding speeds
Sliding distance ; 100 m and counter material ; 304 stainless steel
(a) at 0.08 m/s, (b) at 0.94 m/s, and (c) at 1.98 m/s